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Review

Nigerian Programmes For Modernization From 1985-2018; Success Or Failure

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Abstract: Every government of Nigeria had introduced one form of modernization package or the other up to the present Buhari regime towards better development in Nigeria. This theoretical review presents such programmes and the impact on the people which makes it successful or failure at every tenure of Nigerian government administration. The review also, provides facts that there are success and failures in some many aspect of such programmes though the Nigerians feels less impact of such modern or developmental programmes or that the programmes may be selective but various international indices presents Nigeria as poverty capital of the world which could confirm that modernization programmes might have imparted on some people but the general outcome is still weak. Nigerian leaders should evaluate past modern packages and present a better approach towards improvement by destroying corruption, restructuring, and solving the Niger Delta crisis and Biafra agitation.

Keywords: Modernization, Development, Economy, Social services, Nigeria

Introduction

Edosa (2014) defined Modernization as a particular case of development which has three conditions – a social system that can constantly innovate without falling apart; differentiated, flexible social structures; and a social framework to provide the skills and knowledge necessary for living in a technologically advanced world. Industrialization has been seen as a special aspect of modernization.

Several programmes have been carried out in Nigeria depending on the political leadership and interest of international communities, International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank (WB) inclusive since the inception of Nigeria.

This paper shall give a brief overview of the modernization programmes from 1985 to 2018 with a particular interest the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) that took place between 2003-2007 with a view to highlighting the successes or failures. Finally, there shall be highlights on the hindrances of modernization and possible solutions to better the modernization programmes in Nigeria.

Materials and methods

The research adopted review of various articles, news, press release that are related to the Nigerian programmes for modernization and development from 1985-2018.

Concept of Modernization

The concept of modernization has been subjected to different interpretations based on the orientation/perceptions of the different authors. A school of thought posits that modernization is a systemic process involving complimentary changes in the demographic, economic, political, communication, and cultural sectors of a society. Modernization is a total or complete phenomenon that affects all facets of a society (Ibietan, 2014; Okoli and Onah, 2002). A society is said to be modern when its members use inanimate sources of power or tools to multiply the effect of their efforts. Power refers to the ability to make things respond to ones wishes. Modernization involves a rapidly widening control over nature through closer cooperation among men. In modern societies, people come together to solve problems.

Modernization theory is an economic theory rooted in capitalism which evolved in the 1950s and 1960s. Modernization is a comprehensive theory which deals with the whole process a nation encounters in its attempts of transforming from a primitive to a modernized society. Modernization consists of a gradual process of specialization and separation of social structures, with the aim of promoting efficiency in the developmental process of any society. Modernization theory operates on economic oriented principles which posits that capital formation and investment are the major determinants of economic growth and development. (Adah & Abasilim, 2015)

Within the theory of modernization is the stage model which views development as a process which passes through various evolutionary phases. The main focus of stage model is that development follows certain stipulated framework, as such, nations who seek to achieve economic growth must adhere to this framework. The stage model as described by Rostow (1962), in development is divided into five stages which are; the traditional society, the pre-condition for take-off stage, the take-off stage, the maturity stage, and the stage of high-mass consumption.

The traditional stage is an agrarian society that is not aware of its capability to transform its society to a modern community. They are therefore not willing to take advantage of the potential of modern science and technology. At the stage of precondition for take-off, the society becomes aware of its transformation potential and in turn gets involved in the application of modern science and technology to agricultural and industrial practices. The opportunity for investment and commerce therefore increases at this stage. The take-off stage places emphasis on the eradication of traditional obstacles which hinders economic growth and development. At this stage, the commercialization of agriculture is introduced and investment rises to a maximum level. The drive to maturity stage is a period when the economy shows the capacity to extend beyond the original industries that served as its pivot for take-off. The final stage of development is that of high mass consumption, it focuses on the production of durable consumer goods and services which is marked by a rise in real income. Implicit in the stage model is the assumption that some countries are developed because of their strict adherence to this evolutionary developmental process. The psychological/Idiosyncratic theory is also another strand in modernization theory which attributes development to certain attitudinal personality variables. It is assumed that it is the innovative personality of a nation that stimulates economic growth and development (Adah & Abasilim, 2015; Okereke & Ekpe, 2002).

Just like most theories, the theory of modernization has also encountered various criticisms. The stage model of modernization has been criticized on the basis that development does not follow strictly a particular motion. Thirwall (2011) argues that the stage theory establishes a rigid platform for development and also creates an impression that a nation can attain industrialization only when the agricultural sector has been modernized. His argument revolves on the fact that both agriculture and industries are to grow alongside each other if maximum development is to be achieved. The psychological theory of modernization has been criticized for being psychologically reductionist. It is argued that the theory employs psychological concepts to explain purely sociological problems (Okereke & Ekpe, 2002) which may not work in modernization and development.

Characteristics of the Modernization Process

It is a revolutionary process-implying that the movement from traditional society to modernization involves radical change in patterns of human life. That is, old things have to be abandoned and new ones acquired.

Modernization is a complex process involving all areas of human thoughts and behaviour and cannot be reduced to a single factor or dimension. Its component among others includes industrialization, urbanisation, social secularisation media mobilization, expansion of political participation and increasing literacy (Jhingan, 2007).

Modernization is a systemic process: it is holistic, meaning that change in one phenomenon could lead to change in other phenomenon such as literacy leading to increased awareness.

Modernization is a global process that started around Europe, but has become a worldwide phenomenon. This was brought about primarily by the diffusion of modern ideas and techniques from the European countries to the peripheries and also through internal development of different countries.

Modernization is a lengthy process such that it took Western Europe and other societies several centuries to modernize however it can take a contemporary society lesser time to modernize.

Modernization is a phased process meaning that it is possible to distinguish between different levels or phases of modernization through which all societies will move.

Modernization is a homogenizing process: that is, modern societies have universal values and they share some basic similarities and are interdependent. For example, interdependence among EEC countries.

Modernization is an irreversible process- it doesn't rewind. Modernization is a progressive process: although the cost of modernization is painful, modernization is necessary and desirable because it brings material well-being to the society.

Modernization is a historical process: it is characterized by a step-by-step development in the element of the social system. The process has reached a stage in some parts of the world and this part serves as model for understanding the nature of modernization process. Incidentally, this part of the world is described as the West. However, modernization is not westernization, since every process of modernizing has its own culture and environmental uniqueness.

Approaches to Analyzing Modernization

One of the most popular ways that people have used to analyse the process of modernization is simply to look at or list some of the changes that characterize the process of modernization in presently modern countries of Western Europe, U.S.A and Japan. Here are some of these changes: mechanization of agriculture; greatly improved health due to better feeding and health facilities, highly efficient transportation, sophisticated communication.

Often, these processes are accompanied by rapid urbanization and in government administration; bureaucratic action is guided by planned document. Other changes are widespread availability of educational facilities while merit replaces ascription as a basis of reward (Sharma, Sadana and Kaur, 2012). The second approach in the effort to understand modernization is to list the elements which even though accompanied the process of modernization do not in themselves constitute modernization (Jhingan, 2007). One of this is the fact that modernization is not the same as economic growth. Economic growth construed broadly as an increase in per capita income, is not in itself sufficient a condition for modernization. For instance, Saudi- Arabia, Kuwait and some OPEC countries have very high per capita income but are not considered modern societies. In the same vein, industrialization is not necessarily a condition for modernization. In particular, if we take industrialization to be the application of machines to tasks, then we may say that mining the Zambian copper makes it highly industrialized, Zambia however, is not a modern society.

Modernization is not same as democratisation. However, there exists a link between the technological needs of a modern society with democratic attitudes. For instance, modern technology is employed for mass education and mass mobilization, and without these, democratic institutions may not function well, but this is an indirect link.

Nigerian Modernization Programmes from 1985-2018; Success or Failure

In Nigeria, political modernization has taken various forms and patterns. A litany of such programmes is shown in this place while reviewing the works of Easterly (2001) Ikeanyibe (2009) Onah & Ugwu (2010), Ogbochie (2010) Nwagbara (2011) Edosa (2014) and Obeta and colleagues (2019):

1. The colonial development programmes from 1914-1955 was planned outside the Nigerian region by colonial masters until establishment of National economic Council which has Joint Planning Commission.

2. The fixed medium term programmes

- a. 1st National development planning
- b. 2nd National development planning
- c. 3rd National development planning
- d. 4th National development planning

Within these period, the country was still fragile and programmes was centered on unity and stronger Nigeria. There was effort for public participation. Other programmes emerged within the period which includes:

- i. River Basins development Authority (RBDA)
- ii. Agricultural Development Programmes (ADP)
- iii. Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS)
- iv. Rural Electrification Scheme (RES)
- v. Operation Feed the Nation (OFN)
- vi. Green Revolution (GR)
- vii. Directorate for Food, Road and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI)
- viii. National Directorate of Employment (NDE)
- ix. Better Life Programme (BLF)
- x. People Bank of Nigeria (PBN)
- xi. Community Banks (CB)
- xii. Family Economic Advancement programme (FEAP)

3. The Rolling Plan Programmes (1990-98)

The major programme here is Structural Adjustment programme (SAP).

SAP proposal consisted of:

- i. a 15-20 year Perspective or Long term Plan;
- ii. a three-year Rolling Plan; and
- iii. an Annual Budget that will draw from the Rolling Plan

There was set up the commission for Mass Mobilization for Self-Reliance, Social Justice and Economic Recovery (MAMSER) under Profesor Jerry Gana in 1988.

The programme achieved much but also marred with failures in achieving the goals.

4. Democratic Dispensation Programmes

National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) 2003-2007

NEEDS is targeted to overall development of the country with emphasis on wealth creation, employment generation, poverty reduction, and value reorientation.

NEEDS is anchored on empowering people, creating legal and financial environment that enables Nigerians to make use of the natural resources and flair for business and reforming our laws and way government works.

NEEDS is a home grown poverty reduction strategy that worked from National to State to Local Government as NEEDS, SEEDS and LEEDS respectively.

NEEDS is about people, their welfare, health, education, employment, poverty reduction, empowerment, security and participation of people as the ultimate goal.

The NEEDS vision posits:

Average per capita consumption growth of atleast 2% P.a.

Creation of 7M jobs by 2007

Increase in immunization coverage to 60% by 2007

Access to safe drinking water to average of 70%

Adult literacy rate of atleast 65% by 2007

The NEEDS Programme under Education provides for:

Faithful implementation of free, compulsory UBE law through improvement in education facilities, expanding institutional capacity to produce quality man power

Review School curricular from primary to tertiary institutions to incorporate vocational and entrepreneurial skills including learning ICT.

Establishing of more vocational centers to encourage the embrace of vocational education

The NEEDS Programme under Health provides for:

Strengthening Local Government capacity in public health

Refurbishing Primary Health Centers and making them operational

Establishment of National Blood Transfusion Services

Creation of environment for local drug and equipment production

Redefine roles and responsibilities of FMOH and other Federal Public Structures

Provision of health Minimum Package to Nigerians

The NEEDS under Employment generation targets Agriculture and Rural development, Manufacturing and Small and Medium Enterprises, solid minerals, ICT, Tourism, oil and gas, power education works and housing.

NEEDS targets improving Socio-Economic conditions of women and youths

There were other programmes added during NEEDS:

- i. Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP)
- ii. National Poverty Eradication programme (NAPEP)
- iii. Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC)

It is important to share that NEEDS showed a remarkable achievement in analyzing all the targets. However, the score in the poverty reduction, power supply and employment do not reach pass mark.

Other disappointing scenerios in educational targets includes:

Inadequate funding in technical education in Secondary Schools;

Lack of tools, equipment and tools for effective implementation;

Lack of Electricity;

Inadequate trained and qualified teachers;

Non-challant attitude of government school administrators to programme implementation.

While considering NEEDS-SEEDS-LEADS framework of operation, in September 2006 many states have not finalized SEEDS/LEEDS packages, documentation and training.

Challenges affecting successful NEEDS are unavailable funds, corruption, inadequate capacity of implementation committee, poor monitoring and evaluation process, gaps between participatory methods and finance, lack of political will, lack of NEEDS-SEEDS-LEEDS coordination, lack of continuity in government changes, and absence of Benchmarking

Cultural inhibitions, Laissezfair attitudes towards programmes and irregularities in staff recruitment

Seven-Point Agenda (2007-2010), Transformation Agenda (2011-2015), initiation and implementation of political democratic transition programmes such as those under the regimes of Generals Murtala Mohammed/Olusegun Obasanjo (1975-79), Ibrahim Babangida (1985-93), Sani Abacha (1993-98), and Abdulsalami Abubakar (1998-99).

5. The seven point Agenda are:

Power and Energy – The infrastructural reforms in the power sector was aimed at the development of sufficient and adequate power supply to ensure Nigeria’s ability to compete as a modern economy and achieve full industrialization by the year 2015. That was a declaration of national emergency on energy and power supply. The plan targets increase power supply to 10,000 megawatts (mw) in 2011 and 50,000 mw by 2015.

Infrastructure – At the core of the infrastructural reform is the need to move from an extractive industry fraught with corruption with no value added to the productive sector of the economy. The aim is to free resource deployed through joint venture cash calls for development of the social sector institutions such as education and health. It targeted ending the attendant lack of transparency associated with NNPC operations.

Food Security – Food reforms is primarily agrarian based, anchored on the desire for wealth creation in order to make a shift from the undue emphasis on oil and gas. The emphasis would be on the development of modern technology, research, financial injection into research, production and the development of agricultural inputs. This is expected to revolutionize the agricultural sector leading to a 5-10 fold increase in yield and food production. This will result in massive domestic and commercial outputs and technological knowledge transfer to farmers.

Wealth Creation –This reform is focused on wealth creation through the diversification of production, especially, in the agricultural and solid mineral sub-sectors.

Transport Sector – The transport sector in Nigeria, characterized by poor state and network of roads is an inefficient means of mass transportation of people and goods. Transport reforms would involve road and rail development. This involves the rehabilitation and modernization of the Nigerian railway and the construction of new road network across the country as well as constant rehabilitation of existing ones. The goal is to modernize the Nigerian transport system.

Land Reforms – the main thrust of the land reform is to change the existing land laws and ensure the emergence of land reforms that will optimize Nigeria’s growth through the release of land for commercial farming and other large scale business by the private sector. The final result targets unhindered access to land to boost output and improve capacity for wealth creation.

Security – The assurance of security of life and property is to improve the internal and external investment climate. Thus, security is seen as not only a constitutional requirement but also a necessary infrastructure for the development of a modern Nigeria. With its particular needs, the Niger Delta security issue is the primary focus; organize not with physical policing or military security, but through honest and accurate dialogue between the people and the Federal Government.

Education – The two-fold reforms in the educational sector is to ensure the minimum acceptable international standards of education for all. With that achieved, a strategic educational development plan will ensure excellence in both the tutoring and learning of skills in science and technology by students who will be seen as the future innovators and industrialists of Nigeria. This reform will be achieved through massive injection of both funds and human capital into the Education sector.

6. The Transformation agenda (2011-2015):

Transformation Agenda is a 5-year development plan 2011-2015, driven by a world class team of 28 technocrats under the Chairmanship of the President himself and the coordination of a renowned Economist in person of Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala.

The Transformation Agenda itself is focused on three key areas:

- a. Strong, inclusive and non-inflationary growth;
- b. Employment generation and poverty alleviation
- c. Value re-orientation of the citizenry.

The President used thirteen key sectors as the spring board to work hoping to transform the whole economy of Nigeria. The strength of the Transformation Agenda lie in:

- i. a well thought out policy document;
- ii. a world class Economic Management Team to drive the process though;
- iii. a potential financial, human and political resource base;

- iv. a growing maturity of major institutions of governance such as the National Assembly, the Judiciary, an electoral umpire and the Armed Forces;
- v. the needlessness to re-invent the wheel as several strategic plans blue print are already in place.

Nevertheless, there were a number of threats and challenges to the realization of the Transformation Agenda of which corruption and sabotage was the father of the failure noticed in the modernization programmes

7. Change agenda comes up with:

a. **Anchor Borrowers Programme (ABP)** – this programme made the Central Bank of Nigeria to provide N82 billion to fund up to 350,000 farmers towards Rice, Wheat, Maize, Cotton, Cassava, Poultry, Soya Beans and Groundnut production in about 400,000 hectares of land. Rice mills and fertilizer plants has been established while involving the Private Sector.

b. **The Presidential Fertilizer Initiative** - This involves a partnership with the Government of Morocco, for the supply of phosphate. There are 14 blending plants Revitalized across the country of 2 million MT capacity resulting in annual savings of US\$200 million in foreign exchange, and ₦60 billion annually in budgetary provisions as Fertilizer subsidies. The Scheme enables farmers to purchase Fertilizer with ease and cheaper prices in the country.

c. **Support for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)** through Development Bank of Nigeria (DBN) which took off with initial funding of US\$1.3 billion (N396.5 billion) and is meant to provide medium and long term loans to MSMEs. There is support from the World Bank Group (WBG), African Development Bank (ADB) and European Investment Bank (EIB). World Bank Group and IMF, provided US\$1.3 billion take-off loan and DBN has a N5 billion line of credit available to be accessed by MSMEs.

Bank of Industry has disbursed more than N160 billion in loans since 2016 and has also established a N5 Billion Fund for Artisanal Miners, as part of the Federal Ministry of Mines and Solid Minerals Development's Programme to boost Mining activities in Nigeria.

d. **Social Investment Programme (SIP)**: SIP is the largest and most ambitious social safety net programme in the history of Nigeria, with 140 billion released and more than 9 million direct beneficiaries so far.

e. **N-POWER:** As at August, 2018, 500,000 N-Power beneficiaries had participated and paid N30,000 as monthly stipends. Eze (2019) described N-Power and SURE-P as modern social programmes that had created employment to unemployed masses of Nigeria.

f. **Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP):** N15.183 billion in interest free loans ranging from N50,000 to N350,000 disbursed to more than 300,000 market women, traders, artisans, farmers across all 36 States of the country and the FCT, under GEEP (56 percent of the loans have gone to women). In terms of advancing the financial inclusion goals of the Buhari Administration, GEEP has led to the opening of 349,000 new bank accounts/wallets for beneficiaries and intending beneficiaries. In November 2017, GEEP was chosen as the pilot programme for the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Policy Innovation Unit in Nigeria.

g. **Home Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSFP):** Currently a total of 8.2 million pupils in 45,394 public primary schools across 24 states: Abia, Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi and Imo (South East); AkwaIbom, Cross River and Delta (South South); Osun, Oyo, Ondo and Ogun (South West); Benue, Niger and Plateau (North Central); Kaduna, Katsina, Kano, and Zamfara (North West); Bauchi, Taraba, Borno, Gombe and Jigawa (North East). Over 80,000 direct jobs have since been created from the School Feeding Programme; with 87,261 cooks currently engaged in the 24 participating states. All 36 states of the Federation and the FCT will eventually benefit from the Programme.

h. **Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT):** 297,973 families are benefiting from the CCT Scheme, which pays N5,000 monthly to the poorest and most vulnerable households in the country.

i. **Market Money (Marketmoni):** The FGN commenced this interest free loan to aid small businesses going on in various markets in Nigeria. It is part of GEEP created to provide financial aid for the unbanked and under banked for easy access to loans at no cost except for the 5% administrative fee with a condition to be a member of market association or cooperative society. The loan ranges from N10,000 to N100,000.

The Problems / Hindrances of Modernization in Nigeria

A fundamental problem caused by rapid change or modernization is the strains it imposes on social structures. Rapidly changing societies face problems arising from weakening of traditional restraints on deviant behaviours, breakdown of extended family system, individualism and a loss of cultural identity. These are some of the problems associated with modernization. When these problems do not lead to the breakdown of the social system and society advances, it can be said that there is flexibility of social structures and continuing identity. In a nutshell, modernization can be said to be a process of innovation which manages to be orderly (creative rationality). This as a process is composed of three connected and interrelated ingredients as put by Edosa (2014):

Analytical-causal and Inventive Outlook: This element is considered to be at the heart of the process of modernization. Basically, it is considered to be the scientific approach to the search for and the quest for understanding of social and physical phenomena. By scientific approach, it means the search for the cause and effects of natural events. In other words, nothing happens without a cause, therefore, the approach of modern man is to seek to understand such causes and as a result of such understanding, to find solutions to natural problems. It is this process of searching for cause and understanding effects that enables the modern man to make (innovations) inventions as a result of which he is better able to master his environment. The analytical-causal and inventive outlook is therefore behind all the inventions that characterize modern technological societies. In other words, it reinforces and supports the second ingredient of the modernization process which is the multiplication of tools and techniques.

Multiplication of Tools and Techniques (skills): A modern situation must be characterized by a massive application of tools to everyday processes or actions of getting things done. For instance, the application of technology and modern practices to agricultural productivity; printing; communication; transportation; and provision of basic utilities. But the application of tools is intricately linked to the possession of skills and techniques with which to use machines. But even more significant is the fact that, there must equally be available, the skills for rapidly developing new machineries and techniques. In the absence of good combination of the availability of tools and techniques, there results inevitably a breakdown of existing or acquired machines. Furthermore, such a breakdown is accompanied by a failure to repair or replace such machineries which explains Nigeria's development dilemma.

Flexibility of Social Structures and Continuing Identity: The problems posed by rapid social change, such as the breakdown of traditional sanctions, family systems, ascribed status. The process of modernization recognizes that the problems posed by rapid social change require that social structures be flexible in order to adapt to the requirement of change. Where this is not possible, social structures breakdown. A breakdown of social structure inevitably leads to a loss of social identity as members of the social structure lose their points of focus. The question of flexibility of social structures and continuing identity possess an element of social behaviour. In other words, it requires that social behaviour must adapt and if possible must approximate the functioning of machines, since social tasks are carried out by machines. In this regard, it is important that a modern society display a respect for time (Porter in Harrison and Huntington, 2000). On the whole, social action must be characterized by efficiency which technology demands. Nigeria is yet to achieve a genuine, peaceful, orderly and stable democracy. So also has she been unable to achieve national integration and efficient bureaucracy to deliver public welfare services. Nonetheless, urbanization is rapid and chaotic, literacy, education, and mass media are slowly increasing, but mobile communication has increased exponentially. Finally, industrialization is sluggish, technological growth is in retreat, infrastructures have decayed and virtually non-existent, the economy is poor and undiversified and the people feel a sense of real hopelessness. So, whither Nigeria and its modernizing federal polity.

Policy Inconsistency: this where change of government become change of programmes of government as seen in Obasanjo and Yar'adua era or Jonathan and Buhari government

Politics behind modernization programmes: the political interest matters during any government in power. Mostly programmes are used to settle supporters and affiliates as noticeable in Buhari administration.

Non-political will: the attitudes of modern programme implementers lacks commitment to drive the processes.

Poor implementation design and discipline: the human capacity, instrument, methods, knowledge, technology, equipment, models and modes determines how successful or failure a programme can be actualized.

Corruption: Name all the programmes under discuss ranging from SAP, NEEDS, 7-Point Agenda, Transformation and Change agenda has been characterized by corruption leading to failure of the modern programmes therein.

Modern programme leadership, egocentrism and duality of public policies, cultural and religious factors and misplace priorities (Obi & Okechukwu, 2013) has marred modernization programmes in Nigeria

Solutions towards achieving positive outcome of Modernization programmes in Nigeria

1. Improvement in coordination and collaboration (Anyebe, 2017) in services and operations of government
2. Evolving a sustainable reform in government administration and management
3. Embracing e- governance in stimulation and promotion of good governance for modernization
4. Basic education and literacy on development planning (Uzuegbunam, 2010) towards modernization
5. Reassessment of all modernization programmes towards using the successes and failures as necessary ingredient towards a better programmes than would be very successful.

Conclusion

From the forgoing, the modernization programmes are similar in various ways but only using different nomenclature to distinguish various administrations.

The NEEDS project is an improved version of SAP just as Seven Point Agenda, Transformation agenda and Change agenda are replica of NEEDS but different regime and different political interest while carrying out the targets leading to the difference in performance rating.

All the modernization development programmes had their successes and failures especially NEEDS and it cannot be totally said that anyone is a 100% success or failure. It is also instructive to posit that most of the developmental projects were supported by International Monetary Fund and World Bank (Obeta & Ike, 2019) but the impacts are not well spread across the country.

NEEDS is a laudable programme that should be continued in Nigeria by all administrators whether supported or not supported by IMF and World Bank for better expectations thereby:

1. Improving democratization policies to enhance pro-poor dynamics
2. Encouraging proper funding of developmental activities
3. Effecting coordination and consultation among various implementers
4. Creating political stability and political will by various administrations
5. Avoiding corruption and non-transparency factors

6. Improving Monitoring and evaluation strategies in all programmes
7. Restructuring Small and Medium Enterprises while promoting industrial development
8. Effecting legal backing to poverty alleviation programmes to ensure continuity
9. Finally, the Nigerian government should solve Niger Delta crisis and Biafra agitation.

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Dedication

Dedicated to our families and friends and various Nigerian government leadership who worked seriously for Modernizing Nigeria.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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